

ANALYSIS OF TRAFFIC PROBLEMS OF ENSURING TRAFFIC SAFETY AND SUSTAINABILITY IN TASHKENT

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Annotation

This article is written about the analysis and discussion of the problems of providing road safety and stability in the city of Tashkent. We hope that this article will be useful for many.

Key words: Sustainability, Tashkent, central streets, determined, traffic accidents, amount of movement, direction of movement, vertical direction, horizontal direction, composition of movement and age category.

The risk of getting injured in an accident is higher than that of workers. According to estimates, the route traveled is 1 km The level of danger for pedestrians compared to the car driver and passenger is 4-6 was determined to be high. In comparison to the car driver, cyclists are injured the probability of getting it is 6-9 times higher [1]. According to statistical data, accidents related to pedestrians in the Republic of Uzbekistan the average is 31.3% for regions and 38.6% for cities. Provinces 34.9% of accidents related to pedestrians occurred in Tashkent, the region and in the central cities, indicators related to pedestrians in Tashkent are 40.2% and in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the largest number of accidents with pedestrians occurred in the city of Tashkent. Accidents related to cyclists are on average 6.4% in the regions of Uzbekistan and the region in central cities it is 2.7%. In Tashkent, this figure is 2.3% reaches.

Describing traffic and pedestrian traffic in the organization of safe traffic the research of indicators is the first task.[3] Pedestrian movement amount is measured by the number of pedestrians who passed through a certain road section in a unit of time. Pedestrian traffic is a variable indicator that varies by month, day of the week, and day within hours, it varies by directions and depends on the importance of the street. If 5-6 thousand pedestrians/hour are observed in the central streets of large cities, and on district streets it is 50-150 pedestrians/hour.

We are the object of this research work pedestrian walkways on the main streets of Tashkent and Termiz cities we studied. In recent years, the great Silk Road, Mingbulok and Pedestrian paths on the streets of Ghazalkent are protected from traffic as much as possible not protected. 43 of pedestrians in research facilities in

Tashkent and Termiz the amount of movement was determined by hour and age. To determine the amount of traffic at one-level intersections and intersections of Tashkent city, measurement work was carried out at each intersection and intersection during the peak hours of the working day. In this process, in order to determine how the volume and composition of pedestrians and cyclists are distributed in different directions in each of the selected research objects, this scheme was determined in the form of a scheme, which represents the flow directions of vertical and horizontal streets. Near this regulated intersection there is an underground metro station, a bus station, various shopping and dining complexes. That's why there is non-stop pedestrian traffic here during peak hours of the day.

The amount of traffic is very high in direction A, turning from Mehriqiya Street to Mirzo Tursunzoda Street. The reason for this is that the 3rd station of the Sergeli underground metro line is located at this intersection. Residents living in the area near the metro use the A direction more often when going to work or school. In the table below, we can see the amount of traffic measured during peak hours on 03/16/2022. There are residential buildings, schools and underground metro stations near this regulated intersection. The traffic of pedestrians and cyclists at this intersection is not as dense as at the above intersections. However, the movement of cyclists is observed more. Unlike the two intersections above (the intersection of Mirzo Tursunzoda and Mehriqiyo streets and the intersection of Mirzo Tursunzodava and Shokirariq streets), there are few residential buildings at this intersection, and metro stations are not located at the intersection, but 400-600 meters away from the intersection. In the table below, we can see the amount of traffic measured during the peak hours of the day on 17.03.2022.

One-level regulated junctions on Mehriqiya and Korgontepa streets I learned the amount of movement. In the course of this research, Korgontepa street X direction, Turn from Mehriqiya Street to Korgontepa Street, respectively A, B, S and D I marked it as directions (the directions in the next sections are also in the same order X, A, B, S and D are designated). Residential buildings and shops are located near this regulated junction there is. The number of pedestrians and cyclists at this intersection is low. In the table below, on 15.03.2022 (Tuesday) at the peak of the day we can see the amount of movement measured. From Figure 1, we can conclude that over the course of 11 years, the transport risk in Uzbekistan has been decreasing relative to the number of accidents. Compared to 2009, in 2019 the relative indicator of transport risk decreased by 38%. This indicator came as a result of a decrease in the number of accidents and an increase in the number of cars throughout the region of the country. And also, the relative indicator of transport risk in relation to the

number of the dead also tends to decrease and amounts to 6.6 for 2019. The social risk indicator is 6.3 (2019), while in 2009 it was 7.9 and this indicator has improved by 21%. The severity of the consequences of road accidents has remained at a high level for 11 years and continues to increase. On average, 20-21 people fall victim out of 100 in road accidents. That is, 1 out of 5 people die as a result of an accident. And developed countries (like Germany) 20 years ago had an indicator of 1.4

intersection of Mirzo Tursunzoda and Mehriqiya streets, and Working days at the intersection of Korgontepa and Mehriqiya streets (from Monday to Friday) the total value of the amount of traffic is greater than on weekends (Saturday and Sunday). and at the intersection of Nyagi Sergeli and Mehriqiya streets with values, it is the opposite. The reason for this is that "Sergeli farmer's market" and "Tashkent car" are located near this intersection there are large shopping complexes such as.

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